

Time Base Force (Impulse) Versus Space Based Force ($-dV/dx$) in Classical and Quantum Mechanics Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 29, 2021

In a previous note, we argued that there are two scenarios in classical mechanics, the idea of an impulse $dp = \int F dt$ which imparts the same dp to any p and a $F = -dV/dx$ with $p dp = \int F dx$ which imparts a momentum based proportional to $1/p$. Generally, $F = -dV/dx$ is used in a Newtonian bound problem (e.g. particle on a spring etc), but it is the impulse scenario which yields conservation of momentum. Given that $V(x)$ is used in classical physics, it was also applied to small regions i.e. those of an electron in an atom etc., but non-classical results emerged experimentally leading to discrepancies. In this note like in Part I, we try to retain $V(x)$ on average, but argue that interactions of a single bound particle with a potential should be of the form of statistical impulses. Force $= -dV/dx$ changes p to p_1 in a $1/p$ dependent manner over dx (i.e. at the point x) while an impulse delivers a dp independent of p . Thus, it seems a kind of averaging is needed for impulse p values to create the appearance of an average change in kinetic energy or acceleration. The idea of $-dV/dx$ Function(p, x) is retained for an impulse (as a force), so Function(p, x) is a “piece” of the potential which should be invariant over space and $-dV/dx$ Function should be proportional to p i.e. the hit given. It cannot be a constant, but the next best thing is to have $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, considerations of impulses, invariant in space, may create the appearance of a $V(x)$. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is of the nature of a “probability” and that it has consequences on the “probability” of the single particle with which it reacts. In fact, it requires the single particle to also have a “probability” of $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a probability which is “spread” out over a wavelength, much like a wave in classical physics. Thus, there is the idea of discerning a p at point x as in classical physics versus discerning it over a range of space as in quantum mechanics.

We consider some of these ideas in this note.

Point versus Region Disturbances

In classical mechanics, one considers a point x (i.e. dx about x) at a time. One has $x(t)$, $v(x)$, acceleration(x) etc. Forces act as a particle moves across dx , but the velocity may be approximately measured within x as $v(x)$. The change $dv(x)$ is considered to be a correction and $v(x)$ is taken to be the identity of the particle within dx .

In classical statistical mechanics (including a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (but also a Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein gas)), one considers two body collisions at a point x . Once a gas is in equilibrium, however, one may consider a perturbation which creates more density at one point and less at an adjacent point, i.e. a sound wave. This is now measured over a cycle length and not only at a point. Various sound waves of different wavelengths may interfere to create an overall result for each x point.

In the case of electromagnetism, Maxwell's laws contain spatial derivatives of E (electric field) and B (magnetic field). In establishing the existence of a photon (which has E and B), the d/dx

derivatives must be present ensuring that one has a “disturbance” over a region of space (like a sound wave) and not at a point. For example, without the equations (which yield a wave equation), one might picture a photon as having a fixed magnitude and directional E (and B). The d/dx in Maxwell’s EM equations does not allow for this and so a wave appears as a spatial invariant result which depends on momentum. (We argue that $-d/dx$ in $F=-dV/dx$ in classical mechanics leads to similar consequences for an “impulse piece” of the potential $V(x)$ in quantum mechanics.

Quantum Bound States

In classical mechanics, there are both impulses and accelerations. In the case of an acceleration, $v(x)$ the velocity at x dominates compared to $dv(x)$ and so serves as the identity of the particle. What if one had impulses within dx , however, which were not small? In such a case, one might have a distribution of p 's creating a kind of pave at x . In such a case, one tries to reconcile a picture of impulses with that of an overall acceleration one based on $V(x)$ and $-dV/dx$.

Experimentally, an ensemble of single particle identical states yields a distribution of momenta if the particles are knocked out. These momenta do not match those of the classical mechanical range and suggest a statistical scenario. The particles may be interacting with portions of the potential i.e. receiving impulse hits. It seems one cannot throw away the potential $V(x)$ because it is an experimental description (although perhaps averaged) of these interactions. It seems one must reconcile impulse hits with an average acceleration picture. It was already argued above that $dp = 1/p \int dx F$ which is momentum dependent while $dp = \int F dt$ is momentum independent. Thus, one cannot map impulse dp changes into dp changes from average acceleration over dx . This suggests the impulses are part of the potential and create it when averaged in some manner.

To define an impulse, it is assumed that it is to be represented by a function $g(p,x)$ which is part of the potential with $-d/dx g(p,x)$ yielding a function proportional to p and being invariant in space. It seems that $\exp(ipx)$ is a good candidate as it is invariant in space and has a modulus of 1 so $dp = p$ as a modulus. $\exp(ipx)$ arises because of the use of the derivative d/dx in calculating the force. A derivative d/dx acting on a probability which is what $g(p,x)$ seems to be due to the stochastic nature of impulse hits causes $g(p,x)$ to have structure in space. Thus, one is not dealing with an equilibrium solution at a point (like in two-body collisions) in a gas, but with a spatial probability disturbance similar mathematically to a wave. Like a wave, however, it creates a real resolution in space which may be seen experimentally through humps in the spatial density.

$\exp(ipx)$ is complex and of the form of a wave. This suggests interference which seems convenient because one does not really resolve different p impulses at a point x . In fact, one does not discern these impulses in the potential at all, except for the consequences they have on a particle.

It was argued that an impulse should be part of the potential, but should also be statistical. Thus, $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ suggests that $\exp(ikx)$ is a kind of probability with V_k as a weight. (We have discussed this form in previous notes.) If $\exp(ipx)$ represents a probability then one may use an “AND” condition to link it with a particle. Thus:

$q(p_1+p, x) = \exp(ipx) q(p_1)$ implying $q(p_1, x) = \exp(ip_1 x)$ ((1)) as a solution.

The particle's probability looks just like a piece of potential. This is also convenient because it means that a particle probability of p at x cannot really be distinguished as it combines with various impulse hits from $V(x)$ and changes into a variety of $\exp(ip_j x)$. This is in keeping with particle probability interference as a probability wave. Thus, one has a periodic overall $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $a(p)$ are weights. One cannot distinguish wave type (even probability wave) disturbances at a point, but should be able to distinguish them over space. This leads to the idea that:

$$\int \exp(-ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) dx = 0 \quad ((2))$$

Given that a particle probability $\exp(ip_1 x)$ may be changing into another $\exp(ip_2 x)$ due to impulses at any second, one may consider joint probabilities (as argued in a previous note on joint probability distributions) i.e.

$$\sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1) a(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \text{overall probability at } x \text{ for a bound state} \quad ((3))$$

This overall probability should be $P(x)$. If one integrates over x :

$$\int P(x) dx = 1 = \sum_{p_1, p_2} \delta(p_1, p_2) a(p_1) a(p_2) = \sum_p a(p) a(p) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, $a(p) a(p)$ should be the probability of finding a momentum p knocked out of an ensemble of single particle bound states (all in the same state).

Often there are conceptual issues with trying to follow a quantum particle in space and trying to argue why it is present with more probability at one point than another, but in the impulse picture, one does not need to follow the particle as $x(t)$. Both the impulse and the particle probability have a spatial resolution (wavelength) which is needed to have them create "acceleration type averages" of $V(x)$ and $KE(x)$ at each x point.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that trying to force an impulse scenario at x (with width dx) which already has an "acceleration" picture leads to interesting results. The acceleration picture exists in classical mechanics and is assumed to exist at least as an average in quantum mechanics. The acceleration picture suggests $dp = 1/p \int F dx$ so a change in dp is momentum dependent while an impulse hit yields $dp = \int F dt$ which is momentum independent. The two do not map into each other and so one may think of an ensemble of p values caused by stochastic impulse hits which "somehow" constitute the force $= -dV/dx$ and potential $V(x)$. The question is how to find the function $g(p, x)$ representing an impulse. One may argue that:

$-dg/dx = p$ function1(x,p) but function1 should be invariant and have a modulus of 1. This leads to the unusual result of $\exp(ipx)$ which is complex and describes a wave- a probability wave. Thus, creating an average of impulses which is consistent with an acceleration picture seems to lead to wave mechanics with $\exp(ipx)$ representing a kind of probability. If that is the case, this has implications on the particle probability (as argued in our other notes) that:

$q(p+p1,x) = \exp(ipx) q(p,x)$ or $q(p,x)=\exp(ipx)$ as well. The form $\exp(ipx)$ is not visible in $V(x)$, but it becomes visible in spatial density because an ensemble $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is created. If one suggests that an $\exp(i p1x)$ at x might also be an $\exp(i p2x)$ due to an impulse hit then:

$P(x)= \text{Sum over } p1,p2 \ a(p1)a(p2) \exp(ip1 x)\exp(ip2 x)$ as suggested in an earlier note.

Using $\text{Integral } dx \ P(x) = 1$ leads to discernment of different p values over all space (not a point where they interfere) i.e. $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)a(p) = 1$.